

USE OF ESIM TECHNOLOGY IN THE SECURITY OF ROBOTIC SYSTEMS

Zarif Zafarovich Kodirov

Doctoral Student, Tashkent University of Information Technologies,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Abstract. *The application of information security and eSIM technologies in robotic software applications is discussed. It helps people in different areas of life and they work for people because it is IoT technology and artificial intelligence. eSIM - embedded sim card technology.*

Keywords: *intellect, Human Intelligence eSIM, IoT, Data, Linear Algebra*

Introduction.

"The systems that always help people are Robotic systems. Science fiction or movies are already becoming a reality, and artificial intelligence (AI) is gradually expanding and finding its place in various areas of human life. It is still there to fight humanity. underdeveloped," he said. but it is clear that it is already helping places where the human mind cannot tolerate. Because it is doing so much.

The origins of artificial intelligence

Thoughts create things. Chinese scientists have created an artificial intelligence that plays chess. Historically, the idea of creating an artificial image of man has long been a concern of the human mind. In the Middle Ages, people talked about the possibility of creating a mechanical human-like thinking machine, and chemists developed recipes for growing conscious, that is, artificial humans in some kind of capsule. After a while, a great scientific basis for the possibility of creating artificial intelligence emerged. the French scientist Rene Descartes developed a mechanical theory and created a mechanism.

It is formed close to modern ideas about the functions of artificial intelligence. The English mathematician Charles Babbage wrote the concept of an analytical machine that could calculate chess moves. Leonardo Torres de Quevedo, director of one of Spain's technical institutes, has created an electromechanical device capable of playing the simplest chess games..

Using artificial intelligence in robots Systems

A. Problem solving methods and tools

B. But the real, "artificial intelligence" concept

It is believed to have originated in the 1930s and its creator was the English mathematician Alan Turing. In 36, the abstract Turing computer he proposed was able to perform a number of algorithms correctly, and the computer is still used in many theoretical and practical works. Later, in

the 1950s, Turing tested the machine and said that a computer is faster than a person's intellectual ability.

C. The term "artificial intelligence" itself originated after Turing's death. He appeared in 56 during a conference at Dartmouth University in the United States that brought together leading scholars in the field, and the author was John McCarthy. John McCarthy is the founder of functional programming and the inventor of the Lisp language. Alternatively

D. was explained in Russia in the mid-1950s at a large seminar on "Automation and Thinking" with artificial intelligence at Moscow State University, led by Professor AA Lyapunov. One of the most important achievements of Russian scientists at that time was the development of the Bark algorithm based on this artificial intelligence. In doing so, he simulated brain activity in recognizing shapes.

E. The optimal option to solve the problem with an appropriate interface

In 1965, Joseph Weizenbaum of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology created a computer program called Eliza that performs simple dialogues. For information, the same goes for the Alice or Sahiya program created in Uzbekistan. This is the first modern chatbot. Developed by researchers at the University of Edinburgh in 73, the Freddie robot used artificial intelligence to find and assemble models. And in 79, another prototype of it appeared at Stanford. In the mid-1990s, a new interest in A.I. Perhaps the most famous achievement of the era was the victory of the IBM Deep Blue supercomputer over 97-year-old world chess champion Harry Kasparov.

However, no matter what the developers have achieved, even if the computer is always well versed in solving some problems, it does not mean that this machine is really independent thinking, as many modern scientists believe. Artificial intelligence is a set of methods and tools for

solving various complex practical problems using principles and approaches similar to human thinking. Today, we're talking about programs that typically collect data and learn to classify them, recognize images, text, audio files, and more, and perform a given task better and better each time. That is, about artificial intelligence.

Electrical systems

The concept of teaching artificial intelligence in a small case, rather than suddenly creating a "smart big robot," was born in the Turing era. Machine learning (ML) is designed to identify something else that is not included in the set of examples used for computer training, but has the same features. For example, one of the key technologies for the successful application of machine learning methods is artificial neural systems.

Mathematic Model

Input dataset. X (x) output dataset filter:

$$X2(x) = X(x)/2 - a * X(x-1)/2$$

Here, X2(x) – output

Linear Functions

A Function is special relationship where each input has an output.

A function is often written as f(x) where x is the input:

Methods and means of using eSIM technology in robotic systems

eSIM is a standard developed by GSMA, which allows you to store multiple carrier profiles on a single built-in electronic device (chip) and connect devices to a mobile connection without physical SIM cards. In this case, subscriber profiles of certain operators can be uploaded to eSIM via the network (Internet). eSIM is derived from the English word "embedded SIM", which in Uzbek means "embedded SIM". The introduction of the ESIM standard simplifies the process of connecting tablets, smartwatches, fitness bracelets, robotic systems, portable health systems and other devices to the mobile network. The first products with ESIM-support have entered the market and we can expect new applications this year. Currently, the eSIM standard works in the US and South Korea. A total of 20-25 million people use eSIM-devices.

Mini SIM card

These form factor cards were the next step in the development of the SIM module. The mini SIM card, which is smaller than previous types of cards, has not changed for many years. Dimensions - 25x15x0.76 mm. The mini-SIM card can be inserted into the body of the mobile phone, it can store up to 250 contacts, as well as information about the mobile operator and the

subscriber. So far, some smartphones and most button phones use a mini SIM card.

Micro SIM card

Micro SIM cards are smaller than mini SIM cards. Such cards are also called 3FF. In this case, the number 3 indicates that this type of SIM-card belongs to the third generation modules. We have already mentioned the first and second types of SIM-cards. The micro SIM card measures 15x12x0.76 mm, and the inventors cut out the unnecessary space around the card, leaving only the contact chip that connects to the phone. Most mobile phones manufactured a year or two ago use this type of card.

Nano SIM card

The smallest and at the same time the most popular type of SIM-card available today. The 12.3 × 8.8 × 0.67 mm Nano SIM card (4FF) was approved by the European Telecommunications Institute in October 2012. Operators also offer MultiSim cards, which combine mini, micro and nano SIM-cards for the convenience of subscribers.

The Algorithm of Software.

Programming tools used to create a program

Conclusions

The software is developed in Visual Studio 2019 C # WinForms environment. We used eSIM technology and raspberry in our program. We used ESP8266 WiFi Transceiver ESO32 GPIOs for IoT technologies in control systems Library Collection:

- For consideration in the treatment of ESP32 problems
- How to implement ESP32 access point (AP) for web server
- ESP32 Static / Fixed IP Address
- Get and change ESP32 / ESP8266 MAC address (Arduino IDE)
- ESP32 (OTA) programming - Arduino IDE web update
- Working with solar panels ESP32 / ESP8266 (includes battery management)
- Alexa (Echo) with ESP32 and ESP8266 - Voice-controlled training
- An ESP32 file system boot device on an Arduino IDE
- ESP32 NTP client server: Get date and time (Arduino IDE)
- Publish ESP32 Sensor Readings on Google Sheets (ESP8266 compatible)
- ESP32 Temperature Limit Email (Web server costs)
- Ensuring the operation of All-in-One ESP32 weather stations
- ESP32 IoT Shield PCB with instrument panel for output and sensors

References

- 1.Aldrich FK (2003) Smarthomes: past, present and future. In: Harper R (ed) Inside the smart home. Springer, London, pp 17–39
- 2.Alley R (2013) The drone debate. Sudden bullet or slow boomerang (discussion paper nr. 14/13). Centre for Strategic Studies, Wellington

3. Akrich M (1992) The description of technical objects. In: Bijker W, Law J (eds) *Shaping technology/building society: studies in sociotechnical change*. MIT Press, Cambridge, pp 205–224
4. Archer J, Fotheringham N, Symmons M, Corben B (2008) The impact of lowered speed limits in urban and metropolitan areas (Report #276). Monash University Accident Research Centre (www.monash.edu.au/miri/research/reports/muarc276.pdf)
5. Arkin RC (2009) *Governing lethal behavior in autonomous robots*. Taylor and Francis, Boca Raton
6. Arkin RC (2010) The case of ethical autonomy in unmanned systems. *J Mil Ethics* 9(4):332–341
7. Arth M (2010) *Democracy and the common wealth: breaking the stranglehold of the special interests*. Golden Apples Media, DeLand
8. Asaro PM (2008) How just could a robot war be? In: Briggie A, Waelbers K, Brey Ph (eds) *Current issues in computing and philosophy*. IOS Press, Amsterdam, pp 50–64
9. Bacevich AJ, Cohen EA (2001) *War over Kosovo: politics and strategy in a global age*. Columbia University Press, Columbia
10. Birk A, Kenn H (2002) RoboGuard, a teleoperated mobile security robot. *Control Eng Pract* 10(11):1259–1264
11. Borenstein J, Pearson Y (2010) Robot caregivers: harbingers of expanded freedom for all? *Ethics Inf Technol* 12(3):277–288
12. Breazeal C (2003) Toward sociable robots. *Robot Auton Syst* 42(3–4):167–175
13. Breazeal C, Takanski A, Kobayashi T (2008) Social robots that interact with people. In: Siciliano B, Khatib O (eds) *Springer handbook of robotics*. Springer, Berlin, pp 1349–1369
14. Broggi A, Zelinsky A, Parent M, Thorpe CE (2008) Intelligent vehicles. In: Siciliano B, Khatib O (eds) *Springer handbook of robotics*. Springer, Berlin, pp 1175–1198